

QUALITATIVE CHARACTERIZATION OF NANOCCLAY PARTICLE EMISSIONS FROM PP NANOCOMPOSITES AFTER THERMAL DEGRADATION

Nazanin Alipour¹, Jonas Enebro², Emma Strömberg¹

¹ KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Fibre and Polymer technology,
SE - 100 44 Stockholm, Sweden,
nalipour@kth.se

² SP Technical Research Institute of Sweden
Chemistry, Materials and Surfaces.
SE – 114 86 Stockholm, Sweden

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ABSTRACT

The use of nanomaterials in polymeric materials is a rapidly expanding field, and the polymer nanocomposites are being introduced into various markets. But there is still little known about the fate of nanocomposites and nanoparticles during service life and end-of-life of the materials. To avoid possible environmental, health and safety problems, simulating different scenarios for nanoparticles release from the polymer matrix plays a key role in commercialization of these advanced materials. The polymer/nanoclay nanocomposites show superior material properties in comparison with the pure polymers, such as improved mechanical properties, heat resistance, flame retardancy and decreased gas permeability. Polypropylene (PP) nanocomposites have attracted a considerable interest due to the material's low cost, low density and extensive production volumes. In this study, in order to obtain reliable results regarding the release of nanoclays from PP nanocomposites, homogenous composite with predetermined content of nanoclay was produced and characterized to obtain information regarding content, dispersion and size of the nanoclays in the matrix. The PP nanocomposite was degraded under controlled conditions and the surface morphology as well as oxidation of the material was characterized with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and infrared spectroscopy during degradation. A prototype environmental chamber was designed in order to collect nano-sized particles in a controlled manner and subsequent characterization of the released or formed particles was performed with transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and the exposed nanocomposite was analysed with thermogravimetric analysis (TGA).

1 INTRODUCTION

Nanoparticles (NPs) are increasingly used in composites to improve multifunctional properties of the materials [1]. The extensive development of nanotechnologies requires that the attention is paid to the nanoparticle's potential health and environmental risk [2] to avoid the negative effects and assure the safety of the materials [1]. Several studies report toxicity of nanoparticles and carbon nanotubes (CNTs) when inhaled. Humans could be exposed to nanoparticles in different ways such as during production, service life and disposal [3]. The health risk will be low if nanoparticles remain embedded during and after the service life of the composite [4]. Therefore, it is critical to know and understand the fate of nanoparticles, whether they are released into environment or remain embedded in the

matrix [3]. According to Frogget et al. [5], 83% of today's research focuses on nanomaterial hazard, 16% on potential exposure and around 1% focuses on the release of nanomaterial from nanocomposite during service life, degradation of nanocomposite products and waste management of the materials [4, 5].

The material properties, type of matrix and particles, processing conditions and environmental exposure influence the degradation of the polymer matrix and consequently the fate of nanoparticles after long-term use of polymer nanocomposites [6]. Mechanical impact, degradation due to weathering, aggressive chemicals and fire incident are some of the different scenarios for particles release from polymeric materials. During service life, the material is exposed to different combinations of degradation factors such as UV-light, elevated temperature, water absorption, oxidative environments, etc., all resulting in surface and bulk degradation of the composite [3].

Studies on degradation of nanocomposites containing either carbon nanotubes or silica- and silver-nanoparticles embedded within thermoplastic polymers are common in the research literature [5]. Kaegi et al. [7] studied the release of silver-NPs from acrylic paint in a controlled experiment. The material was exposed to ambient weather including different rain cycles and the water samples were collected after each cycle. He established that 80% of vanished silver NPs, were released during the first two months of weathering and TEM revealed that the released particles were attached to the organic binder. To study the effects of UV, several thermoset nanocomposites with silica-NPs and CNTs have been exposed to Simulated Photo-degradation via High Energy Radiant Exposure (SPHERE) chamber. The authors reported rapid degradation and mass loss of the epoxy matrix, resulting in gradual increase in the mass fraction of silica-NPs on the surface of the material. This in turn might influence the release of silica-NPs from the degraded matrix. However, no direct evidence of released silica-NPs embedded within the matrix or dissociated was found. In contrast to the results for silica-NPs, the nanocomposite surface was covered with a dense layer of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs), which prevented further degradation of the nanocomposite and remained on the surface even after prolonged exposure to intense UV [5, 6].

Wohlleben et al. used a standard ISO weathering method [8] to test several nanocomposites such as polyomethylen (POM) with CNTs and polyamide (PA) with amorphous silica-NP. In contrast with SPHERE method no accumulation of silica-NP was observed after UV exposure, however, rapid surface accumulation of CNTs, as well as increased degradation of POM-CNTs was established. Vilar et al. [9] studied the degradation effect of modified and non-modified MWCNTs. The TGA results showed loss of organic compounds from PA-6 with non-modified MWCNTs but not from the composite with modified nanomaterial after 1000 hours exposing to accelerated weathering conditions. The results also implied that PA-6 matrix became more resistant to weathering by incorporation of modified MWCNTs. According to Frogget et al. [5], in 92% of the studies where the release occurred, matrix particles were detected, in 76% of these studies nanomaterials were partially embedded within matrix and the particles were detectable. The dissociated nanomaterials were detected in about 30% of these studies. Most weathering studies focused on the release of carbon nanotubes or on silver-, silica- and titania- nanoparticles. Less attention has been paid to nanoclay composites. Nanoclays have a large surface area and improve fire resistance, mechanical and barrier properties due to their layered structure [10]. Thermal degradation of nanoclay composites have shown that initial degradation temperature shifted to higher temperature, improving the life cycle of the nanocomposite, but due to higher amount of residual impurity in the polymer matrix, they show faster degradation process.

The purpose of this study was to develop a methodology for evaluation of nanocomposite degradation, in this case polypropylene (PP) with 5wt% nanoclay, under controlled conditions and investigate how nano-sized particles are formed or released during the degradation of polymer nanocomposite. To achieve this objective a prototype chamber was designed for stimulation of degradation conditions and collection of degradation products in a controlled manner.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Material

The polypropylene homopolymer (PP), with density of 0.908 g/cm³ and melt flow index (MFI) of 8 g/10 min at 230 °C, was supplied by Nexeo Solutions (Borealis, PP HD120MO). Polypropylene nanocomposite (nanoMax-PP) was provided by Nanocor. The nanoMax-PP contains approximately 30% nanoclay, determined by TGA. The nanocomposite containing 5 wt% of nanoclay (PP-5wt%Clay) was manufactured through mixing of PP and nanoMax-PP in a micro-compounder (DSM Xplore 15 ml) at 200 °C and 100 rpm for 3 min.

2.2 Sample preparation

The produced PP-5wt%Clay was compression moulded to 1 mm thick sheet in a TP400 Fontijne Press (Vlaardingen, Netherlands) at 220 °C by first applying 50 kN compressive load for 2 min and thereafter 320 kN compressive load for 8 min. The films were cooled to room temperature at a cooling rate 10 °C min⁻¹ while maintaining the compressive load.

2.3 Ageing

The PP-5wt%Clay was pre-aged in an ULE-699 ventilated oven (Mettler, Germany) at 100 °C. Rectangular pieces (60×20 mm) were prepared and aged in the oven prior to subsequent degradation in the chamber. The ageing process was monitored with FTIR.

2.4 Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

The oxidation induction time (OIT) was measured by DSC-820 (Mettler-Toledo) at 150 °C. Each sample with a weight of 5±0.5 mg was placed in a 40 µl standard aluminium pans with three holes in the lid to allow the transport of nitrogen and oxygen gas to the sample. Specimens were kept at 25 °C for 5 min for a nitrogen purge to eliminate any residual oxygen and then were heated to 150 °C at a rate of 20 °C min⁻¹ in nitrogen with a flow rate 50 mL min⁻¹. When the set temperature had been reached, the sample was equilibrated for 5 min before the atmosphere was changed to oxygen. The oxidation induction time was determined as the time of the intersection between the isothermal baseline and the tangent deviation from baseline at 0.2 Wg⁻¹.

2.5 Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

Reflection infrared spectra were obtained using a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum 2000 FT-IR spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer Inc., USA) equipped with a MKII Golden Gate single reflection ATR system with a diamond crystal. The spectra were based on 16 scans from 600 to 4000 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

2.6 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The cross sections of fractured samples in liquid nitrogen (LN₂) and surface of aged samples were examined in a field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, Hitachi S-4800, Japan). The layered-structure was evaluated on samples coated with a thin layer (5 nm) of platinum-palladium using a Cressington 208HR sputter coater.

2.7 Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

The nanocomposite structure and the degraded products were studied by transmission electron microscope (Hitachi HT7700, Japan). The PP-5wt%Clay was embedded in epoxy resin and cured overnight at 60 °C. The 50 nm thick sections were cut using RMC cryo ultramicrotome and placed onto copper grids and also the degraded products were collected with the copper grids from the Isopore membrane. The grids were transferred to the TEM and the sections were observed at 80 kV.

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The dispersion of the nanomaterial in the matrix is of high importance to assure reliable degradation profile of the nanocomposite. The scanning electron micrographs of compression moulded PP-5wt%Clay showed homogenous dispersion of clays in the matrix (Fig.1).

Figure 1: Scanning electron micrographs of a) Pristine PP b,c) PP-5wt%Clay

The oxidation induction time (OIT) value PP-5wt%Clay at 150 °C was 26 min. The results from FTIR analysis clearly showed clay peaks in range of 900 to 1100 cm^{-1} . Figure 2 presents comparison of pristine PP and PP-5wt%Clay composite.

Figure 2: IR spectra of pristine PP and PP-5wt%Clay nanocomposite

The samples were pre-aged in the oven at 100 °C, prior to insertion into the chamber. The pre-

ageing step was added to study the degradation behaviour of the material and shorten the exposure time in the chamber. FTIR results didn't show any oxidation peak on the surface of samples that were aged at 100 °C for 14 days. Degradation of the PP-5wt%Clay started at the edges of the samples and a carbonyl peak at 1715 cm^{-1} , representing oxidation of the material was determined by FTIR analysis (Fig.3). It should be mentioned that pristine PP didn't show any degradation at the edges of the samples even after prolonged time of ageing. The OIT values for PP-5wt%Clay were reduced from 26 min (un-aged sample) to 10 min after 10 days of ageing at 100 °C.

Figure 3: a,b) PP-5wt%Clay nanocomposite after ageing at 100 °C c) IR spectra after 10 days of ageing of PP-5wt%Clay nanocomposite at 100 °C

The degraded pieces of the samples were collected on the filter paper and carbon tape and analysed with SEM. The SEM micrographs showed that the nanoclays were still embedded in PP-5wt%Clay nanocomposite after degradation.

Figure 4: Degraded PP-5wt%Clay nanocomposite after 14 days of ageing at 100 °C

Chamber design:

In order to characterize the particle emissions from nanocomposite during simulated service life, a prototype glass chamber was designed. The chamber was enclosed in a heating element to simulate thermal degradation (at 100 °C). The sample was attached freely hanging from the top of the chamber. The degraded and released products were collected on isopore membrane (polycarbonate) with 100 nm pore size (Fig.4). The purity of the inlet air was assured by a HEPA filter mounted to prevent airborne particles inside the chamber and a constant airflow through the chamber was established. The degradation products collected from the membrane and the exposed sample surfaces were analysed with SEM and TEM.

Figure 5: Isopore membrane a) surface with nanoclay particles b) cross section

The chamber will in the future be adjusted to simulate different exposure environments, as shown in the schematic design of the chamber (Fig.6). The goal is to study degradation of different nanomaterials and matrices, creating a reliable method for evaluation of material deterioration during service-life of the products.

Figure 6: Schematic design of the exposure chamber

4 CONCLUSION

The thermal degradation of PP-5wt%Clay nanocomposite was simulated in a prototype exposure chamber to evaluate the release of nanoparticles. The pre-ageing step is necessary for better understanding of the material degradation and calibration of the duration of the experiment. Clay nanocomposites showed rather fast degradation and the degraded products were collected and analysed. The chamber design enables the study of different degradation factors individually or combined. The methodology will be developed further to study degradation under various conditions.

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